

Supplementary Material

The role of exposure window and dose in determining lead toxicity in developing Zebrafish

Vittoria Curcio[†], Rachele Macirella[†], Settimio Sesti¹, Abdalmoiz I. M. Ahmed¹, Federica Talarico², Roberto Pizzolotto¹ and Elvira Brunelli^{1*}

¹ Department of Biology, Ecology and Earth Science (DiBEST) - University of Calabria, Via P. Bucci 4/B, 87036, Rende, Cosenza, Italy; vittoria.curcio@unical.it (V.C); rachele.macirella@unical.it (R.M); settimio.sesti@unical.it (S.S); abdalmoiz.ahmed@unical.it (A.I.M.A.); roberto.pizzolotto@unical.it (R.P.)

² Natural History Museum and Botanical Garden, University of Calabria, 87036 Rende, Italy; federica.talarico@unical.it (F.T.)

* Correspondence: elvira.brunelli@unical.it

† Vittoria Curcio and Rachele Macirella contributed equally to this work and are the co-first authors

Figure S1. Survival (%) of zebrafish larvae exposed to 2.5 and 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of Pb in both early (a) and late (b) exposure. Kaplan–Meier survival graph: the symbols represent the different treatment groups; Log-rank (Mantel–Cox) Test was used to compare the survivals during the whole exposure period.

Figure S2. Larval length in zebrafish larvae exposed to 2.5 and 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of Pb in both early (a) and late exposure (b). a = significance of low concentration group with respect to control group; $*p \leq 0.05$ b= significance of high concentration group with respect to control group; $***p \leq 0.0001$ c = significance of high concentration with respect to low concentration group; $**p \leq 0.001$.

Figure S3. Eye volume in zebrafish larvae exposed to 2.5 and 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of Pb in both early (a) and late exposure (b). a = significance of low concentration group with respect to the control. b = significance of high concentration group with respect to the control. c = significance of high concentration group with respect to low concentration group. * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.005$; *** $p \leq 0.001$; **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Figure S4. Severity of the spinal curvature in zebrafish larvae exposed to 2.5 and 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of Pb: early (a) and late exposure (b). a = significance of high concentration group with respect to control group; b = significance of low concentration group with respect to control group; c = significance of high concentration with respect to low concentration group; d = significance of 96 hours treatment with

respect to 48 hours or 144 hours treatment with respect to 96 hours; * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.005$; *** $p \leq 0.001$; **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Table S1. Eigenvalues after Correspondence Analysis.

Eigenvalues	Dim.1	Dim.2	Dim.3	Dim.4
Variance	0.102	0.030	0.023	0.007
% of Variance	62.7	18.6	14.5	4.1
Cumulative % of Var.	62.7	81.4	95.9	100

Table S2. Contribution and square cosine of variables to 1st and 2nd dimension.

	1st dimension		2nd dimension	
	%contribution	cos2	%contribution	cos2
Tail	60.9	0.887	23.1	0.1
Spinal	1.8	0.118	17.5	0.34
Pericardial	28.0	0.619	53.5	0.351
Yolk	0.5	0.03	0.1	0.003
Cumulative	8.7	0.648	5.7	0.126

Table S3. Contribution and square cosine of treatments to 1st and 2nd dimension.

	1st dimension		2nd dimension	
	%contribution	cos2	%contribution	cos2
A2_5-48	5.6	0.386	0.2	0.004
A2_5-96	6.3	0.523	3.7	0.09
A2_5-144	8.7	0.687	8.8	0.205
A5-48	11.6	0.932	1.7	0.042
A5-96	20.2	0.98	0.7	0.01
A5-144	24.9	0.859	13.6	0.139
B2_5-48	4.8	0.655	0.1	0.002
B2_5-96	7.4	0.652	4.5	0.116
B2_5-144	8.3	0.668	2.8	0.068
B5-48	0.04	0.003	42.8	0.944
B5-96	0.6	0.093	11.4	0.557
B5-144	1.5	0.203	9.8	0.393